

GENERAL GUIDELINES ON USING ROBOTS TO SOCIALLY ENGAGE AUTISTIC CLIENTS: THE USER-CENTERED/ROBOT SOCIAL ENGAGEMENT (URSE) MODEL

By Noel Kok Hwee Chia & Patricia Mui Hoon Ng

Noel KH Chia, an approved IACT trainer, is an associate professor of special education at the National Institute of Education, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore. Ms Patricia MH Ng works as a part-time lecturer/tutor as well as research assistant at the National Institute of Education, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore.

The revised set of criteria of autism spectrum disorder (ASD) provided by the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders-5th Edition (DSM-5; American Psychiatric Association, 2013) has excluded Asperger Syndrome and Pervasive Developmental Disorder-Not Otherwise Specified. However, the new definition has not put an end to the ASD epidemic, whose international prevalence rate of 60 per 10,000 is applied across cultures. In the United States, its current prevalence rate is estimated to be an average of one autistic in 110 children. In Singapore, an increase by 46% from 361 ASD cases in 2005 up to 528 reported in 2010, and ASD knows no racial, ethnic, or social boundaries (e.g., family income, lifestyle, and educational levels) (Chia & Chua, 2014).

As more and more individuals are identified with ASD, it becomes very common for teachers and healthcare practitioners (e.g., therapists, counselors, social workers and psychologists) to come in contact with such clients. The biggest challenge when working with such clients is to engage them socially. Therefore, it is important to understand how an individual with ASD thinks and interacts with others within a given social context.

Re-framing ASD from the Socio-cultural Perspective

Today, the most commonly used perspective on ASD is the medical view which has defined the condition as displaying a triad of impairments in social interaction, communication and imagination. The current DSM-5 criteria of ASD looks at its onset in terms of the “[S]ymptoms observed in early developmental period (may not manifest until social demands exceed limited capacities)” (Chia & Chua, 2014, p.4) and its qualitative impairment is expressed in terms of “[P]ersistent deficits in social interaction and communication as well as deficits in social-emotional reciprocity and social relationships” (Chia & Chua, 2014, p.4).

However, ASD is seldom viewed from the socio-cultural perspective, which defines the condition as reduced

amounts of social engagement – reduced levels of social interaction and social communication, fewer friendships and less play” (Conn, 2014, p.2-3). In other words, ASD is a genetic condition that exhibits social challenges and affects how individuals interact or relate to one another. Hence, depending on which preferred perspective on ASD one chooses to accept, ASD can be regarded as a mental disorder, social difficulty, developmental disability and so on.

In this new millennium, more and more countries are pushing for an inclusive society. According to Slee (2001), *being and becoming inclusive* implies accommodation rather than assimilation of all individuals irrespective of need or disability and places the burden of change upon the society than the individual. As a result, healthcare practitioners now need to be more critically aware and reflective in terms of involving themselves in greater depth of thought on issues relating to inclusion and of adapting to changes in their daily activities and social interactions.

The societal support for inclusion of people with ASD in the community should be seen to embrace the social need “to maintain a balance between providing ordinary experiences of relationships and shared communication within natural contexts and the strategic application of support and training of specific skills and social understandings” (Conn, 2014, p.117). Many conventional strategies/approaches (e.g., the TEACCH method, the Picture Exchange Communication System, comic strips and video modeling) have been developed to promote social experience, which can take many different forms such as “in written texts, images, cultural practices, ideas, routines and so on” (Conn, 2014, p.118). Moreover, there are also claims that complementary and alternative approaches (e.g., dolphin-assisted therapy and mega-vitamin therapies) could help to promote social development, which covers a wide range of functioning (e.g., communication, social understanding, self/other awareness and play). It is important that healthcare practitioners be mindful that many of these latter approaches have not been evidence-based or scientifically proven.

However, most of the current strategies/approaches have omitted the physical presence of another individual or dictated that the communicative partner acts in highly structured and/or socially predictable ways (Conn, 2014). In other words, the social experience for individuals with ASD becomes less authentic, less rich, less dynamic, and instead, becomes more artificial, simpler and straightforward and hence, supposedly, becomes more comprehensible to the individual with ASD. That is not what the real world is like and how it actually works in our daily encounters with others in different social contexts.

The autism education today focuses on the pedagogical approaches that can be asocial, social and/or non-social, where “social learning involves teaching that is delivered in ordinary ways” (Conn, 2014, p.117). For example, the use of visual instruction or computer-based program to complete a given task is asocial; teacher-directed instruction or oral interaction within a class lesson is social; and completing a jigsaw puzzle is non-social.

Socially-based Approaches/Strategies for ASD

Today, there is still a disagreement among the practitioners and researchers if an individual with ASD has fewer “social scripts” (see Bauminger, 2004, for detail) than non-autistics or they are over-scripted and therefore, too unauthentic or artificial in their social responses (see Burack et al., 2001, for detail). Socially-based approaches/strategies for working with individuals with ASD often aim to slow down, simplify and delineate socio-cultural experiences. As a result, Conn (2014) argues that these approaches/strategies reduce the “very rich, continuous and multilayered social processes to more manageable amounts” (p.118).

The explanation why these socially-based approaches/strategies fail to address the social challenges of individuals with ASD is twofold. Firstly, autism is not a disorder per se but a complex condition with co-morbidities as well as tensions among the different and even conflicting perspectives. Secondly, human behavior is complex and is determined by many factors such as feelings, experiences and perceptions. Hence, it is very important to explore how ASD should be best understood within a socio-cultural context in order that healthcare practitioners working with such clients can get a holistic account of social functioning of an individual with ASD and his/her responses to the immediate environment as well as others in addition to the multi-layers of influences from the community at large.

With the introduction of information and communication technology (ICT), more options are available to healthcare practitioners from which they can select whichever tools they find work best with their clients with ASD. No two individuals with ASD are alike in all aspects as autism is a complex spectrum disorder with varying degrees of severity. There are those who respond best when interacting with internet chatter robots – also known as *chatbots* (e.g., Cleverbot). Others may prefer to take the role of an avatar in a virtual world to establish contact with other gamers or

players. There are also those who prefer to communicate through Chat-room, i.e., real-time online chat and online interaction with other internet users individually or in a group.

Socially Assistive Robots

One fast growing domain of applied robotics research is the socially assistive robotics (SAR), which emerged from the huge research literature on robot assistance involving social rather than physical interaction. The benefits of SAR can be extended to geriatric care (for elderly, elderly disabled and disabled elderly), special education (for individuals with social and cognitive challenges, e.g., ASD and intellectual and developmental disorders) and rehabilitation (for those with physical and sensory challenges), among others. According to Fong et al. (2003), SAR is the intersection between assistive robotics (i.e., robotics focusing primarily on assistance) and socially interactive robotics (i.e., robotics focusing primarily on social interaction).

In this paper, we described briefly about socially assistive robotics (SAR) and how it can help to improve social engagement of individuals with ASD. Our main aim is to establish a comprehensive Human-Robot Interaction (HRI) framework with proposed general guidelines on social interaction between an individual with ASD and a socially assistive robot. Hopefully, whatever social competence (or sociability) attained through SAR can be transferred and applied to any social context.

Figure 1 illustrates our proposed HRI framework consisting of (1) the user with ASD, (3) the user persona and (3) the socially assistive robot. We call this framework the User-Centered/Robot Social Engagement (URSE) model for ASD.

Figure 1
User-Centered/Robot Social Engagement Model

User-Centered Design

User-Centered Design (UCD) is a multi-phase problem solving process that attends to a user’s needs, wants, as well as limitations of a product, service or process at each phase of the design process (Norman, 2013). Moreover, it predicts how the user is likely to use a product or service, analyzes the findings and assesses the validity of the assumptions basing on the actual user behavior in. In the URSE model, the assessment is essential in order to understand intuitively what the user with ASD in HTI experiences and what his/her learning curve is like.

Users: The users in this URSE model are individuals identified/diagnosed with ASD. As already mentioned earlier, we have adopted the socio-cultural perspective to define ASD.

UCD Guidelines: In the URSE model for ASD, UCD seeks to find out how a user with ASD responds to HRI in a given scenario. The following questions serve as general guidelines to help practitioners facilitate social engagement with their clients with ASD:

- Who is the user with ASD of HRI?
- What are the user’s social experience goals and the social tasks he/she needs to perform?
- What is the user’s social experience level with HRI?
- What social functions does the user need from HRI?
- What prior social experience and skills might the user need, and in what form does he/she need them?
- How does the user think HRI should work?
- What are the extreme HRI scenarios?
- Is the user multitasking?
- Does HRI utilize different input modalities such as visual, auditory (aural and oral), haptic (gestures and orientation), olfactory and gustatory?

Interaction Design

The Interaction Design (IXD for short) has been defined as “the practice of designing interactive digital products, environments, systems, and services” (Cooper, Reimann, & Cronin, 2007, p.610). It involves synthesis and imagining things as they might be, more so than focusing on how things are. The term was first coined by Bill Moggridge and Bill Verplank in the mid-1980s to focus on behavior such as satisfying the users’ needs and desires to use a product or service. According to Norman (2013), the focus of IXD is “upon how people interact with technology” (p.5).

User persona: A user persona represents the goals and behavior of a user with ASD. It is synthesized from data collected from interviewing the user. The aim of a user persona is to develop a precise description of the user with ASD and what he/she wishes to accomplish in HRI.

IXD Guidelines: In the URSE model, the goal of IXD is to provide the following general guidelines to facilitate the understanding of a user with ASD in his/her social engagement during a HRI session:

1. What can be done during a HRI session for the user persona with ASD to be socially engaged?
2. (a) What is most likely to be happening (in social learning process) to a user persona with ASD during the HRI session?
(b) What is most likely to have occurred (in social experience) to a user persona with ASD during the HRI session?
3. (a) What is happening (in social learning process) to the user with ASD during the HRI session?
(b) What has just occurred (in social experience) to the user with ASD during the HRI session?

Laws of Robotics

Several studies (e.g., Alers & Barakova, 2009; Chia & Li, 2012) have shown that individuals with ASD love technological gadgets since they are stimulated and challenged to communicate using them. With recent advancements of robotics, robots are becoming more sophisticated and closer to resembling human. The Turing Test (Turing, 1950) can be administered to determine a robot’s ability to exhibit intelligent behavior equivalent to, or indistinguishable from, that of a human. While we are aware of other principles of robotics (see the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council, 2011, for detail), we have chosen to adapt Isaac Asimov’s three classical laws of robotics (LoR) as general guidelines to govern the role of SAR in the URSE model.

LoR Guidelines: In the URSE model, we adapted LoR to pose the following questions as general guidelines for practitioners when using SAR:

1. How does SAR promote positive social engagement in a user with ASD without adverse or negative effects?
2. What social algorithm does SAR need to obey and follow without conflict with the First Law?
3. What constraints will SAR encounter during a HRI session that may cause erroneous functions and thereby resulting in conflicts with First or Second Laws?

Conclusion

In the years to come, robotics will advance by leaps and bounds. The roles of robots will be extended into many areas of applications impacting our daily lives. The healthcare practitioners’ attitudes and understandings are essential to effective implementation of SAR in their professional practice. They may have to work collaboratively with these humanoid robots (see Pictures 1 & 2), for instance, to help provide their clients with ASD the social skills they need.

A humanoid robot

The authors in the NTU Robotics Lab

Continued on page 18

ly added to the existing belief system about ourselves, it can be very difficult to change a belief – even with conscious re-evaluation. Instead, we tend to prove our current set of beliefs to ourselves by noticing which of our experiences confirm those beliefs and ignoring or rejecting the elements that counter those beliefs.

One of the intuitive needs of a human being is to feel wanted and valued. Children seek attention from their parents for validation, and sometimes parents are not able to provide that attention. When a child – or even an adult – feels unwanted, the feeling automatically becomes a negative auto-suggestion. The belief created leaves a very insecure self-image in the unconscious mind and lasts for a lifetime.

Children themselves can be cruel to each other because they often establish their own identity at the expense of other children in the family. Imagine a scene where a very young child is attempting to play with older children. The older child calls for the mother to come and take the younger one away saying, “He’s no good! He can’t play with us. He is too little.” Because of the undeveloped perceptions of the younger child, he is not able to logically analyse that statement. The emotional belief input is that he is just not good enough. He doesn’t reason that when he is older he will be as skilful at that activity as the older children are; he simply believes he is ‘not good enough’. These are the unconscious belief systems that are being formed, and the thoughts and feelings we experience in response to these events continue into adulthood.

Within the mechanism of the conscious and the unconscious, a simple system of cause and effect is working. I believe that too many people complicate the human mind. The unconscious mind is born with its unconscious instincts for self-preservation and pleasure, but all the information used in its programming (to form beliefs) is received from the conscious mind. The memory bank in the unconscious gathers together all the information received during a lifetime and creates from it the subconscious belief system, which can be called a silent partner to consciousness.

The unconscious mind follows any belief impersonally and with equal efficiency. Much of life’s creative process happens without our conscious knowledge. There are conscious and unconscious forces operating in our lives. The mind does not decide which thought it should act on. Whatever the conscious mind believes, whether the belief is true or not, the unconscious mind will act upon that belief. The unconscious follows any belief with equal efficiency – impersonally.

General Guidelines on using Robots to socially engage Autistic Clients: The User-Centered/Robot Social Engagement (URSE) Model

Continued from page 9

References

Alers, S.H.M., & Barakova, E.I. (2009). Multi-agent platform for development of educational games for children with autism. *In Proceedings of the International IEEE Consumer Electronics Society’s Games Innovations Conference 2009* (pp.47-53). August 25-28, Imperial College London, UK.

American Psychiatric Association (2013). *DSM-V diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders (5th Ed.)*. Washington, DC: The Author.

Bauminger, N. (2004). The expression and understanding of jealousy in children with autism. *Development and Psychopathology*, 16, 157-177.

Burack, J., Charman, T., Yirmiya, N., & Zelazo, P. (eds.) (2001). *The development of autism: perspectives from theory and research*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.

Chia, N.K.H., & Chua, A.C.K. (2014, Spring). A brief examination of an autistic mind: From mindsight to mind blindness, from mindfulness to mindlessness. *Unlimited Human!* 4-7.

Chia, N.K.H., & Li, J. (2012). Virtual dolphins for children with autism: Design of a generic questionnaire for reflective evaluation of a virtual reality-based intervention. *International Journal of Special Education (online)*, 27(3), 45-53.

Conn, C. (2014). *Autism and the social world of childhood*. London, UK: Routledge.

Cooper, A., Reimann, R., & Cronin, D. (2007). *About Face 3: The essentials of interaction design*. Indianapolis, IN: John Wiley & Sons.

Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (2011). Principles of robotics. Retrieved from: <http://www.epsrc.ac.uk>.

Fong, T., Nourbakhsh, I., & Dautenhahn, K. (2003). A survey of socially interactive robots. *Robotics and Autonomous Systems*, 42(3/4), 143-166.

Norman, D. (2013). *The design of everyday things*. New York: Basic Books.

Slee, R. (2001). Inclusion in practice? Does practice make perfect? *Educational Review*, 53, 113-123.

Turing, A. (1950). Computing machinery and intelligence. *Mind*, LIX (236), 433-460.

“Thank you for the great service! I am so blessed to be a certified member of your organization and always recommend you to my colleagues.”

Carolyn Paige, Santa Barbara, CA